

ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS USED AT
ELEMENTARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF DISTRICT GHOTKI

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the English language teaching methods used in the Government secondary schools of District Ghotki. This Study is based on a Quantitative approach. Data for this current study were collected through a survey using a closed-ended questionnaire from nine government secondary schools district of Ghotki. After that data was entered into a data sheet for statistical and descriptive analysis. The result was drawn through giving charts, bars, and percentage marks. Study found that the grammar translation method is the most usable in the elementary and secondary schools of District Ghotki.

INTRODUCTION

English as a Second Language

Human beings have an instinctive tendency to speak a language, and Language is a means to communicate our thoughts, desires, and feelings. It is the most sophisticated product of the human mind. Language helps in shaping the identity of individuals and also serves as a stronger marker of society. All human beings take their birth into such linguistic environment where they learn their mother tongue through an acquisition system. However, more than six thousand languages are spoken in the world, and having command over one language is not sufficient in today's era. The world is rapidly growing into multiple spheres, so there is a dire need to be multilingual. Among all languages of the world, the English language possesses the dominant position.

Now Learning the English language has become essential to access the global avenues.

The English language is known as a lingua franca. It plays the role of a bridge between two non-native speakers. The Germanic dialect of Small Island appeared in the world as a global language today. English is broadly used in different sectors, Schools, colleges, and universities. It is also the language of electronic media, newspapers, and radio. The English language is not source of communication but also opens new avenues for job purposes. From Primary school to industrial organization, the English language has shared its insignificant value. It plays a paramount role in bringing socioeconomic prosperity to the geographical region.

In order to be well-versed in it, different theories and approaches are proposed by many scholars, philosophers. They attempt to seek how the English language should be taught to Second language Learners. Krashen (1989) states that there are two independent systems to learn language: the learning system and the acquisition system. Learning system occurs in a formal setting, while acquisition happens in a natural environment. However, Behaviorists have opinions that language learning is an imitation process. Learners just need to get the input from society, while Mentalists have the belief that children are biologically hardwired to develop their language. They have an innate aptitude to learn their language with the help of the Language Acquisition Device (LAD). Thus, learning and teaching the English language also undergo the same hypothesis. Numerous methods, approaches and strategies to teach English language have been proposed and each method possess both the strong and drawback features, such as GTM (Grammar Translation Method), DM (Direct Method), ALM (Audio lingual Method), CLT (communicative language teaching), Suggestopedia, TPR (Total Physical Response), and Silent Way.

English Language Methods

GTM (Grammar Translation Method)

The grammar translation method is known as a classical method that was used to translate classical languages like Greek and Latin. It is a traditional method. The major focus of this method is teaching a language on the basis of rules and regulations. Grammatical rules are taught deductively. The English language has four skills: speaking, listening, reading, and writing, but in the Grammar Translation Method, Reading and writing skills are taught to learners. This method plays a vital role in improving reading comprehension level. States that reading is the heart of language. Vocabulary is taught to learners through a bilingual word list. Translation is completely allowed in this method. Students learn the translation from L1 to L2. Techniques like translation of sentences or passages, reading text, and memorization of words along with synonyms and antonyms, are applied in this method. With the strong points of this method, it also possesses a few drawbacks, such as language skills like listening and

speaking are completely ignored. A large number of grammatical rules are taught, which puts the language learners into complexity.

DM (Direct Method)

The name of this method itself suggests that meaning should be conveyed directly without going through the process of translation. Translation is not allowed in this method. All the concepts related to language learners are taught only in L2. No cramming material is provided to language learners. This method only focuses on communicating with learners in the target language. Vocabulary is taught naturally. No list is provided to learners for memorization. This method enhances the communication skills of language learners and also improves the pronunciation skills of learners. Dialogue practice is mostly made through this method. Major grammatical concepts are taught inductively. Techniques like reading text aloud, conversation skills,

CLT (Communicative language teaching)

Communicative language teaching is such an approach that focuses on interaction. The main aim of this method is to enable the learners for communicative purposes. Through this, students become engaged in conversation, role play, and do activities in problem-solving. Students can develop their listening, speaking. Reading and writing skills by the utilization of this approach. This method does not teach only grammatical rules to learners but also enables them to communicate fluently. In this method, errors made by learners are considered a natural phenomenon and are corrected. This method requires a high level of language proficiency from teachers for English language Teaching. This method develops communicative competence rather than linguistic competence. Role play is a major activity of this method that helps the learner improve communication skills. This method is a student-centered approach.

ALM (Audio lingual method)

The main purpose of this method is to teach language based on the drilling technique means repetition is a major strategy of this method. This method specifically focuses on the listening and speaking skills of learners. Through this, the pronunciation of

learners is improved, and new material is taught in dialogue form. In this method, teachers hardly use to first language in the classroom. This method follows the behaviorist theory that language learning is an imitation process. Repetition, memorization, and giving positive feedback are major tenets of this approach. According to the method, language learning is a habit formation process. Grammatical concepts are learnt through activities or by continuous practice.

Along with the strong points of this method, it has a few drawbacks. One of the major drawbacks of this method is that more attention is paid to productive skills rather than receptive skills of language; reading and writing skills are ignored in this method. The second weak point of this method is that it puts too much emphasis on drilling and repetition techniques for learning language.

TPR (Total Physical Response)

This method refers to teaching English through the coordination of speech and action. This method was proposed by Dr. James Asher. According to him, language learning also occurs through physical activity. In this method, along with describing anything, the Teacher physically performs the action. Students are engaged to learn the language through physical gestures. In this method, teachers and students both play the role of actors. Learners learn the grammar inductively.

Statement of problem

The problem statement is a clear and concise summary of the research problem, typically contained within one paragraph, its function is to identify the concerned issue (Ahmad et al., 2024). English is a Lingua franca that plays a vital role in communication. Many methods are proposed to teach the English language. Each method has advantages and drawbacks. Ghotki, a district of Province Sindh, is famous due to its industrial sites, which include mixed educational institutions, government and private schools, and colleges. These institutions face the unique challenges regarding English language teaching methodology. To find out which method is mostly used in secondary classes of district Ghotki to teach the English language has prime importance. The study also evaluates the perception of students

regarding the teaching methodology of English Teachers.

Literature review

Literature review is a written overview of major writings and other sources on a selected topic. Sources covered in the review may include scholarly journal articles, books, and websites. The purpose of literature review is to gain an understanding of the existing research and debates relevant to a particular research topic (Rao et al., 2023; Sadaf et al., 2024). Many scholars have made efforts to analyze the teaching methodology of the English language and try to explore the issues and challenges faced by language learners. Awan and Shafi (2016) conducted a study on the English language teaching methodology of DG Khan schools. The result of their study shows that mostly teachers adopt the GTM in their classes because the Grammar Translation Method is the most effective method to teach the English language, rather than the direct method. (Rahimjon Oglu 2025) made a study of different methods of English language teaching and highlighted the strong and weak points of each method. His study shows that all methods have advantages and disadvantages, but the choice to adopt in the classroom depends upon the needs of language learners, the classroom setting, and the availability of resources. (Hussain, Nawaz et al. 2022) argue that many English language teachers use very traditional techniques to teach the English language. He suggests that instead of implementing traditional ways like “chalk and Board”, modern tools should be utilized to teach the English language. Ilyas (2019) conducted a study on the importance of the ICT system in the teaching and learning process. He states that ICT resources play a vital role in educational institutes. He emphasized to utilize the ICT tools in the Government schools of Sindh for effective teaching methodology. Khan (2020) has views that modern era, teachers of the English language still use a prescriptive approach in their teaching process. His result shows that mostly teachers, particularly from Government schools, apply older techniques and strategies in the English teaching process. The teaching methodology of English teachers is very traditional because they still use the GTM method. Islam, Husain et al. (2024) clearly describe that the traditional method of language teaching is ineffective

and also puts language learners into complexity. He states that the utilization of older techniques not only proves ineffective but also makes the language learning and teaching process so uninteresting. By applying the old method, students become passive learners instead of active. Intarapanich (2013) presented his views that CLT, TPR, and GTM are effective teaching methods and helpful in the English language learning process. He defines that, along with the teaching of grammatical rules, other techniques must be adopted in the classroom, like Word games, role play, dialogue practice, presentations, reading aloud, etc. Mohammad, Masum et al. (2018) state that English teachers adopt such teaching methodology of the English language as applied in other subjects like Social Studies and General Science. In this approach, the Classroom becomes teacher-centered. No chance is given to language learners to develop their communication skills, and they show poor performance in the language learning process. He adds his opinion that the reason for his utilization of this approach is due to a lack of resources in the classroom. According to Imtiaz (2014) issue of STR and the unavailability of technological tools (Audio-visual) in secondary schools of District Ghotki has also become a cause for poor results in the English language learning process. In the government secondary school of district Ghotki, there are more than 45 students present in the classroom, which shows a dismal picture of the education system, and due to this large ratio of students, the learning process of the English language can be quite difficult for teachers. So, there is a dire need to adjust 38 students per classroom to get the enormous output.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is the part of the research study in which researchers give an account of the research methods, which they have used to conduct their research (Arshad et al., 2025; Yousaf et al., 2025). This study uses quantitative approaches. We have done a survey by distributing closed-ended questionnaires, which is a research tool of a quantitative approach. Quantitative approach is used for statistical analysis of numerical data. In this study, closed-ended questionnaires provide the structured responses of participants and which can be quantified. After that, we have tried to explore the strategies and the most

commonly used method by English language teachers at government schools of the district of Ghotki.

Data collection

Data was collected from nine schools of the district Ghotki by conducting a survey. Questionnaires regarding the teaching methodology of the English language were distributed among teachers and students. First questionnaires were distributed among English teachers, and second questionnaires were provided to students. More than 25 English teachers participated from different schools to give the answers to the questionnaire, whereas the second questionnaires were distributed to 200 students from different schools. In addition to observation was made in the classroom during the English subject.

Sampling

The study uses simple random sampling. Sample sizes of students are 200, which represent the whole population of district Ghotki Students. However, sample sizes of teachers are more than 20, which represent all English language teachers of district Ghotki. The research instrument that is applied in the study is a questionnaire, which proves an efficient way to find out which method is mostly used to teach the English language at elementary and secondary schools of District Ghotki.

Research Design

“Design of the research comprises of the whole procedure which is conducted research” (Ahmad et al., 2022). This research follows the descriptive and correlational research designs. These research designs are adopted to discuss the current practices of the English language and the impact of teaching methods on students at elementary and secondary schools of District Ghotki.

Data analysis

The collected data for this study has been analyzed through an Excel data sheet, through giving charts, bar and percentage marks. A data sheet is used to draw a comprehensive result in a statistical way. In order to find which method is mostly used in elementary and secondary schools of district Ghotki, Pie charts and marks of percentage are given to check the most adopted method in English language classes.

Analysis of teachers' survey

The questionnaire consisted of 30 questions related to different teaching methodologies of the English language. Each method had 09 questions and every question had five choices to be selected: agree, strongly agree, disagree, strongly disagree, and neutral. In response to questions of all teaching methods, 90 percent of teachers preferred to use of Grammar translation method in the classroom, while 5 percent of teachers favored the direct method in their schools, and five percent of teachers supported the communicative language teaching method. A survey was made to explore the most commonly used teaching methods for teaching the English language in elementary and secondary schools of District Ghotki.

The results showed that GTM is the most used method for teaching the English language to the students of the elementary and secondary schools district of Ghotki. According to English teachers, students of district Ghotki belong to ESL learners, so that they are easily taught through the translation process, which is the main feature of the GTM method. It was also noted through the survey that teachers mainly focus on the reasoning and writing skills of learners. According to English teachers, reading and writing are skills that are building blocks of language. So these skills are mainly focused and taught to students of the elementary and schools district of Ghotki. The result is shown in a pie chart.

Student's survey

Another questionnaire was distributed among the 200 students of the elementary and secondary school of District Ghotki. Students were asked to share their perception of the teaching methodology of English teachers. Through this survey, it was found that students of elementary and secondary schools of district Ghotki prefer to learn the English language through the grammar translation method. According to them, GTM helps them to improve their reading and writing skills and enables them to make translations from L1 to L2. In response to particular questions, students enhance their vocabulary through bilingual word lists. Out of 200, 140 students were in favour of the GTM method, whereas the remaining students ignored the GTM method and supported

other ELT Methods. 60 Students shared the major drawbacks of the GTM method and chose to learn the English language through modern ICT tools, but the majority of students prefer to learn the English language through the translation process. Hence survey of students regarding teaching methodology showed that GTM is widely adopted by teachers to teach the English language, and according to the opinion of students, GTM proves to be an effective teaching method in the English learning process.

Conclusion

This study found that English language teachers mostly use the grammar translation method in elementary and secondary schools of District Ghotki. According to English language teachers, the Grammar

translation method is the most effective method for English language teaching. Study found that through this method, students develop their reading and writing skills and learn the grammatical rules of language. However, students of elementary and secondary schools of district Ghotki are also interested to learn the English language through the translation process. Instead of asking many questions, they prefer to lecture method. The study also found that students want to learn the English language through a deductive approach and develop their grammatical rules as well.

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